

ASSESSMENT OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE PERFORMANCE OF MOBILE MANUFACTURING COMPANIES:

A CASE STUDY OF TECNO MOBILE

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Published Date: December 2017

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Chapter one is the introduction part of the study. This chapter presents the general idea of the background of the study, statement of the problem, research questions and objectives of the study, significance of the study, scope of the study, limitation and organization of the study.

1.1 Background of the Study

The contemporary consumption environment is characterized by advancements in technology, the need for hyper-connectivity via social media and a wide array of goods and services (Lingle, 2013). In the past, consumers had limited choices and consumed whatever was available in the marketplace in the production-driven society (Dahl, 2000; Friedman, 2000; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Today's global consumer is spoiled for choice and may even dictate what goods and services should be provided as he uses his consumption habits to reinforce his individual identity (Castells, 1997; Friedman, 1999), often in the form of lifestyle choices. Consumption practices are no longer dictated by traditionally ascribed 'identity categories' of class, race and ethnicities (Crook, Pakulski & Waters, 1992). Rather, consumers are influenced by the dynamic changes in their micro (family and local landscape) and macro (global landscape) environments (Lewis, 2007). The empowered consumer of today makes his consumption decision against the backdrop of globally accepted practices within the constraints of a local social context. Advancements in communication technology and the presence of global media add to the complexity of connecting effectively with consumers.

The highly fragmented consumer market presents several challenges for mobile company. Firstly, a one-size-fits-all market strategy is not a viable and sustainable option for the long term as market conditions continue to be locally differentiated (Robertson, 1985; James & Howells, 2001). Prior research also supports that consumers tend to define their social contexts locally rather than globally (Dahl, 2000). This suggests cultural influences. As such, corporations must have in-depth knowledge of each local context (country) in order to make a successful connection to the local consumer. Within each local environment (country), there are cultural differences and lifestyle differences to be considered. Also, the changing dynamics in the macro and micro-environments through the course of life provide additional challenges. Secondly, with

lower costs and wider product offerings, it is becoming increasingly difficult to capture the attention of the consumer.

Manufacturers that are successful in this aspect are those who adopt targeted segmentation strategies to accommodate life cycle changes and truly engage with their customers. All these are part of customer relationship management techniques employed to make an emotional connection to consumers. Thirdly, the pervasiveness of social media as part of the contemporary hyper-connected society (Lewis, 2007) adds another level of challenge as corporations have to interact directly with the consumers in order to provide a personalized and engaging user experience (Daye, 2010; Sutter, 2012; Lingle, 2013).

Thus, In order to thrive in such a dynamic business environment, companies need to adopt successful customer relationship management strategies. This often means knowing how and when to ride with important consumer trends in order to forge a meaningful and sustained relationship with consumers. Because, the mobile phone is one of the ways in which corporations may effectively reach out to their target audience in each local context. Indeed, the mobile phone is fast evolving to be a signifier of modern everyday living. This worldwide phenomenon is manifested in several major global developments.

The last two decades have seen dramatic changes in mobile communications technology and the resulting changes in how people communicate. The growth is particularly staggering in developing countries with little “landline” telephone infrastructure. Many remote areas in the third world have gone from having no telecommunications infrastructure to having satellite-based communications systems. The International Telecommunications Union (2013) estimates that there are about 6.8 billion mobile subscriptions with mobile penetration rates of around 128 percent in developed nations.

While the technology behind the mobile phone may be global, cultures, values and lifestyles are not (Leonardi, 2002; Lewis, 2007). The local context determines the socio-cultural fit of the product in question. For instance, in China, people rarely react to the loud phone conversations (Plant, 2002) while in Japan, train commuters are constantly reminded via the public announcement systems to switch their mobile phones to ‘silent’ mode to maintain the tranquility of the environment (Campbell, 2007; Canton, 2012). Mobile phone usage patterns accentuate the

social differences between people of different cultural backgrounds and are tightly correlated with the various purposes of the social actions as well as the different situations, social relationships and social roles (Geser, 2004). Even the types of mobile phone devices differ from country to country which suggests that the micro-environment (local context) has a greater impact on mobile consumption. The mobile devices are split into three main categories. Smartphones are those with or without touch screens. Multimedia phones are those with touchscreen and/or QWERTY keyboard but without an advanced operating system. Feature phones have no touchscreens, QWERTY keyboard or advanced operating system. Understanding the cultural norms of each local context will enable businesses to devise suitable marketing campaigns to effectively connect with their customers. The high penetration rates are a clear indication of the mobile wave and its impact on today's hyper connected world (Saylor, 2012). Access to real-time information allows users to magnify their knowledge and make more informed decisions while on the go. Given such global developments, it is imperative for firms to understand how local consumers are influenced by micro environmental and macro environmental factors in order to be more effective in their consumer communications. This is the premise of this research.

For the postmodern consumer, consumption is not just about using things but the production of identity-constructing experiences through the usage of products (Firat & Dholakia, 1998). The focus of this study will be specifically on the factor affecting mobile manufacturing companies with regards to consumer consumption of mobile phones and how it relates to identity-construction.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The rapidly increasing importance of the international business environment has led companies to invest in trying to better understand how the macro and micro-environmental factors affect consumption and the role that culture, specifically consumer identity plays in the consumption process. In turn, they can build on more effective global marketing approaches to connect with their target audience. The tide of popular opinion as to how to market internationally has swung between the multi-local or adaptation premise, which presupposes that consumers in each country market are different, to the standardization premise which presupposes that consumers around the globe are similar (Briley, Morris & Simonson, 2000). The mobile phone stands at the

center of this debate. A modern navigation tool determining the coordinates of everyday living (Lasen, 2003; Rudich, 2011; Haddon & Green, 2010; Goggin, 2011), it serves as a representation of contemporary communications technology infused with traditional values. Consumer behavior with regard to mobile phone consumption is a combination of universally accepted norms (the macro-environment) as well as social etiquette guided by the local context (the micro-environment). While the technology behind the mobile phone may be global, cultures, values and lifestyles are not (Leonardi, 2002; Bell, 2004; Lewis, 2007). There have been several studies covering the micro and macro-environmental influences on mobile phone consumption (Plant, 2002; Lasen, 2003; Geser, 2004; Prichard, 2004; Taylor & Harper, 2003; Ling, 2001; Alexander, 2000) indicating that there are global norms as well as local differences in the mobile phone consumption patterns of various cultures.

The studies also support the relationships between culture, consumption and technology in relation to consumer identity. Even though some of these studies were conducted over a decade ago, the fundamental theories with regard to culture and mobile phone consumption are still relevant today and still applicable to the mobile phone landscape. However, given the short history of the mobile phone, there have not been many specific in depth studies examining the link between mobile phone consumption and consumer identity in the context of both the global and local environment factors. This is important because consumer identity is tied to the interplay between culture, consumption and technology. Existing studies, some sponsored by mobile phone giants like Nokia, Motorola and Ericsson, focus on how consumers from different cultures are using their mobile phones. This understanding enables them to design mobile phones that consumers want. There have also been several comprehensive studies about how youths are embracing mobile phone technology and how it affects their growth and development (Prichard, 2004; Taylor & Harper, 2003). While mobile marketing companies such as Nielson and MobiThinking provide mobile statistics on what global consumers are using their mobile devices for, there has been little published data on the link between mobile phone consumption and consumer identity. Based on existing literature on mobile phone consumption, there is evidence to support the cultural implications of the mobile phone. Lasen's (2003) exploratory study of mobile phone use in public places in London, Madrid and Paris indicates cultural differences in the way people use their mobile phones and what mobile phone behavior is considered culturally accepted etiquette. Crabtree, Nathan and Roberts's (2003) study "Mobile UK – Mobile Phones

and Everyday Life” researched on the past and present of the mobile phone through the current practices of everyday life, providing a clear indication of the likely future of mobile devices and applications in the United Kingdom. Plant’s (2002) research “On the mobile – the effects of mobile telephones on social and individual life” provided a great overview of how people around the world are using their mobile phones. Bell’s (2004) ethnographic research explored some of the ways mobile technologies are shifting function and form in the Asian context. In sum, all these studies support that macro and micro environmental factors do play a part in influencing how an individual consumer uses his mobile phone. There have, however, been no existing studies investigating which environment – the micro or macro plays a greater part in influencing a consumer’s mobile phone behavior. In addition, there seems to be little research on how corporations, other than those in the mobile communications industry, can leverage this knowledge to better connect to their consumers. This is particularly relevant as advancements in communication technology continue to evolve and aid in the conduct of everyday life.

1.3 Research Question

1. Does consumer mobile phone consumption behavior depend on factors in the micro-environment in Tecno Mobile?
2. Does consumer mobile phone consumption behavior dictated by the dynamic changes in the macro-environment in Tecno Mobile?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

1.4.1 General Objectives

To investigate the effects of micro and macro environment factors affects Tecno mobile manufacturing company with regards to consumer consumption and individual identity.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

1. To evaluate the micro environment factors effects on Tecno mobile manufacturing company with regards to consumer consumption and individual identity.
2. To evaluate the macro environment factors effects on Tecno mobile manufacturing company with regards to consumer consumption and individual identity.

1.5. Significance of the study

This work is supposed to draw attention for those in the Mobile manufacturing companies to know and give attention to some of the effects that contribute for consumer consumption and individual identity, so that they can allow implementing strategic marketing management and as such improving on productivity. Generally, this study has both theoretical and empirical contributions to academics and management practices respectively.

1.6. Scope of the Study

This research is mainly will focus on examining the Factors affecting mobile manufacturing company with regards of consumer consumption and individual identity with specific focus as follows

1.6.1 Geographical scopes

This research will undertake examining the Factors affecting mobile manufacturing companies with regards to consumer consumption and individual identity with specific focus on Tecno Mobile Company, in Addis Ababa the company head office.

1.6.2 Time Horizon/scope

This study primarily focuses on research related to mobile manufacturers. The research was conducted within the time frame from November 2016 G.C. to June 2017 G.C. and has since been expanded for general publication

1.6.3 Conceptual Scopes of the Study

The researcher stick to investigate the Factors affecting mobile manufacturing company with regards of consumer consumption and individual identity that is generally concerned in examining and explaining of Micro and Macro environment which includes social networks, personal history, symbolic meaning of products and globalization for the specific case of Tecno Mobile Company

1.6.3 Methodological Scopes of the Study

- ▶ The source of information for the research is organizational members involved directly in the manufacturing process, managerial staff and also non managerial employees.
- ▶ The research relies on both primary and secondary sources of data.

1.7 Limitation of the Study

This research main limitation is that it is focused on one mobile manufacturing factory namely TECNO mobile so it doesn't take into consideration other companies and other factors.

In the course of the research, the researcher encountered a lot of problems such as follows; Difficulty in accessing information from respondents, the researchers found it difficult to get information from its respondents more especially from high level officials of the project stakeholders.

Some respondents were unwilling to give help as to give relevant information for the research. The other potential limitation of the study was time constraints. This was due to the bureaucratic system of the organizations. Therefore, willingness and verbal approval of high officials of the stakeholder organizations was needed before any research could be conducted for interview purposes. This affected the time in which this research was supposed to be finished in the time provided.

1.8 Organization of the Thesis

This research has been organized in five chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the entire thesis, and it covers the background of the study, statement of the research problem, the objectives of the study and the significance of the study. Chapter 2 is devoted to presenting a review of the literature related to conceptual issues. Chapter 3 covers the research design and methods, which will be employed and the method used to collect data for the research. Chapter 4 covers analysis of the data gathered and provides a solid interpretation to these data. The final chapter assesses the findings of this study, draws the conclusion and important recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO: RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter presents a review of the related literature on mobile manufacturing industries relationship marketing presented by various researchers, scholars, analysts and authors. The review of literature of the study tries to provide the theoretical perspective and conceptual analysis of factors affecting mobile manufacturing industries relationship marketing in mobile companies. Moreover, the study addresses, what the literature says on the determinant factors of mobile manufacturing industries relationship marketing

2.1 Theoretical Frameworks

Here we discuss the relationships among culture, consumption and technology as they relate to consumer identity are examined based on existing research. It deals with the theoretical foundations of this study to provide a rationale for using ‘culture’ as a central link to consumer behavior. It provides the background to the origins of culture, consumption and technology and explores the relationships among culture, consumption and technology. For the scope of this study, attention is restricted for the purposes of this study, the factors are confined to those relating to micro environment social networks, personal history and symbolic meaning of products. Similarly, factors related to macro environment globalization. An understanding of the research issues necessitates an appreciation of the core theoretical areas of culture, consumption and technology and how they relate to the factors.

2.1.1 Consumption

Daye (2010) believes that what we consume defines who we are. Hogg and Michell (1996, pg.629) define consumption as the “search for, choice, possession and disposal of goods and services”. Belk (1988, pg. 139) believes that “possessions are a major contributor to and reflection of our identities”. Carrier (1995) suggests that material things are a way to define who we are to ourselves and to others. Contemporary consumption is characterized by the fragmentation of markets and the media, which has led to a blurring between the formerly clear-cut entities of producer and consumer. One of the most significant developments in the global consumption environment is the dynamic changing role of the consumer. Once a passive recipient of whatever was available in a production-driven economy (O’Connor, 1997), today’s consumer can dictate to a certain extent, what they want to consume and thus, what corporations

should be produced (Friedman, 1999). Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) suggest that today's consumption is about co-creating value, with the active participation of both the producer and the consumer. Consumption is no longer viewed simply as a financial or utility-driven activity but as a force in the creation of meaning and expression of identity for individuals (Daye, 2010). The link between consumption and self-identity has been established in past research. Social scientists Bauman (2000) believe that possessions are the way people define themselves in their search for self-identity. This self-identity development is not conceptualized simply as a linear process but an iterative evolutionary process (Kleine & Kleine, 1999), continually reordered against the backdrop of shifting day-to-day experiences (Harkin, 2003).

Kleine and Kernan (1991) believe that past experiences (personal history) and daily transformations (everyday life) as social interactions play equal roles in contributing to a person's sense of self. That is, the meaning people ascribe to a consumption object is influenced by both its personal significance and the amount of external context. Consumption opens up to new interpretations and uses (Miller, 1997) as consumption practices become established and acquire meaning over time (everyday life). The belief that well-being can be enhanced through one's relationships with objects is not a new concept. It fulfills a need and also conveys what is embedded within social structures. Through the consumption of objects, one can utilize the object in question as well as reinforce one's identity within one's social network. This view is supported by Baudrillard (1988) and Bourdieu (1984) who believe that the motivation to consume goods and services correspond to the meanings they generate for the individual within his social network as objects build self-identity (Belk, 1988). Each of us is motivated by needs and each of these needs must be satisfied in turn, starting with the first – need for basic survival. Only when the lower order needs of physical and emotional well-being are satisfied will individuals be concerned with the higher order needs of influence and personal development. All these relate to self-identity at the various stages in life. Contemporary consumption is most noticeably associated with the concept of materialism - widely viewed as an important life value (Mick, 1996). A defining characteristic of highly materialistic individuals is a belief that well-being can be enhanced through one's relationships with objects (Burroughs & Rindfleisch, 2002). Bauman (2000) argues that consumption today is about wants and the need for immediate gratification. The increasing need for possessions also corresponds with an individual's multiple roles in contemporary society. The traditional view of the consumer as the passive recipient of all

that marketing offers by way of products, services and communications, has shifted to the recognition that the consumer is an active player in his own consumption. In a globalized world where an increasing number of goods and services are available for choice selection, consumers can choose their identities through the consumption process (Warde, 1994) in the context of a social network. Choi (2002) adds that consumers constitute their identities increasingly on the basis of their active consumption of products offered to them through leisure, media and consumer goods industries. Each consumption decision represents how the individual is expressing his identity to the outside world as he continually re-creates his identity (Slater, 1997) through the course of life. In summary, the contemporary consumption environment has given rise to changes in the traditional roles played by both the producer and the consumer. The advent of globalization has increased the choice of goods and services consumers have and has empowered the consumer to better express his identity through the consumption process. This is because possessions are the way people define themselves in their search for self-identity. As the process is one that is iterative and evolutionary, corporations have to co-create and define value with the consumer in order to provide what the consumer wants in the marketplace.

2.1.2 Culture and Consumption

This section expands on the previous section on consumption and examines the part that culture plays in the consumption process and how it relates to consumer identity. Specifically, this means that culture has a part to play in the consumption process. Culture affects consumption desires, motivations and symbolic meanings consumers attach to products and relates to both collective and individual identity (Dahl, 2000). Culture also encompasses artifacts and products (Dahl, 2000) which corresponds to Baudrillard's (1988) theory that an individual seeks order within a society from objects. In turn, material objects will influence an individual's scope of options and hence influence his practices and development of experience. In this sense, the goods and services consumed by an individual and the ways in which they are consumed create meanings for the individual and for those within his social network (Bourdieu, 1984; Baudrillard, 1988). Research has demonstrated that people tend to conform to the majority opinion of their membership groups when forming attitudes. Briley, Morris and Simonson (2000) suggest that cultures endow individuals with different rules/principles that provide guidance for making decisions and a need to provide reasons that activate such cultural knowledge. Burroughs and

Rindfleisch (2002) adds that consumption is a culturally accepted means of seeking happiness, success and the populist notion of the good life. While cultural studies used to presuppose a passive cultural consumer, recent research looks at the way a cultural product is received, reconfigured and reused by consumers according to their own needs (Ger & Belk, 1996). Relativists argue that some understandings and emotions are unique to a particular culture, and that the meanings and functions may remain permanently beyond the comprehension of outside observers of the foreign culture (Edgerton, 2000). Shweder (2000) adds that membership in some particular tradition of meanings is an essential condition for personal identity and individual happiness. As such, while marketing their services and products internationally, successful enterprises must form a strategy that allows for cultural differences even though they may not be part of traditional marketing (Eramus, Kok & Retief, 2001). This 'cultural standard' defines what belongs within a culture and what is perceived as 'alien' and thus unacceptable. This may explain why certain products are readily accepted into cultures while others take time or never gain acceptance. Indeed, today's local cultures are a mix of local particulars and global universals as represented by the micro-environment and the macro-environment respectively.

The emergence of a 'cosmopolitan' culture is the best example of contemporary consumption in relation to culture. This so-called 'world culture' seems to be driven more by consumption practices rather than by traditionally ascribed 'identity categories' of class, race and ethnicities (Crook, Pakulski & Waters, 1992). The subject is invited to find his identity no longer in pre-given structures and ascribed roles but by means of his consumption to make, to create and to design himself. Thus, the consumption environment is a mix of local particulars (unique to individual cultures) as well as global universals (standards commonly accepted) as represented by the micro-environment and macro-environment respectively. Today's consumer is able to create his identity based on his consumption practices. He is able to maintain traditional values associated with his ethno-cultural identity while reconciling with the demands of a globalized world. This in turn creates a unique consumer identity. The micro and macro-environments are interconnected because contemporary culture is a mix of both local particulars as represented by factors relating to social networks, personal history and the symbolic meaning of products as well as global universals as represented by factors relating to globalization. This in turn, creates a unique consumer identity.

2.1.3 Culture, Consumption and Technology

Having discussed the role that culture plays in consumption, this section focuses on the interplay between culture, consumption and technology as they relate to consumer identity. According to Friedman (1999), contemporary society is rapidly transforming into one shaped by mobility as characterized by the fluid movement of capital, labor and information globally. As a consequence, consumers' perception of time and space has changed considerably. In a world of ever-changing and increasing technologies, the concept of 'doing more with less' has become a reality as consumers harness the power of information technology to aid them along in their daily lives (Castells, 1997; Friedman, 1999; Dahl, 2000; Lasen, 2003; Bell, 2004; Tchouaffe, 2009; Rudich, 2011; Sutter, 2012). Friedman (1999) adds that consumers of today have embraced information and communication technologies in many aspects of their lives. Interestingly, sometimes the technological product and the service it provides are used in ways unforeseen by designers, makers and sellers of the product.

Consumers buy what technologists design and often fashion innovative uses around them (Crabtree, Nathan & Roberts, 2004). The measure of a product's success lies in how far it diverges from its creator's intention. The social context influences how individuals make sense of what they do with technology as reflected in how individuals incorporate technology into their everyday life. The frequent occurrence of unanticipated uses of communication technologies (Rogers, 1995; Scott, Quinn, Timmerman & Garrett, 1998) suggest that technology use is often influenced by social practices. Leonardi (2002) states that technologies are always understood in cultural contexts. Researchers today have begun to show how behavioral patterns regarding technology are shared among members of a culture. Not only do such groups construct people's meanings of technology, they continually define and reposition it throughout the changing contexts of life (Barley, 1986). In fact, because no technology inherently makes sense for a given cultural system, the social group ensures that there is a socio-cultural fit of the technology (Widman, Jasko & Pilotta, 1988). Indeed, technological devices and their systems of use are part of the material culture of a society. At the same time, they serve as the instruments with which individuals use to conduct their daily lives. The way that technology is used is the result of how people project their respective social world onto the technology (Lasen, 2003). This relates directly to the social identity of individuals. Jamison and Hard (2003) suggest that the

appropriation of technology from a cultural perspective is the adoption and modification of a technology to fit with the respective cultural environment of a particular group. According to Barnett (2005), in the bid to understand how people live and employ technologies, cultural anthropologists are on staff at most large technology companies like Microsoft, British Telecom and Intel. At IBM for instance, the research group that includes anthropologists and other social scientists has grown from 8 in 2003 to about 60 in 2005. This reflects how cultural differences can affect the design of technology. Bell (2004) believes that while underlying technologies may be the same across societies, the ways different cultures employ technologies have undergone radical shifts and repurposing as new technology is adapted within a culture and used to support existing patterns of behavior. At the other end of the spectrum, there have been criticisms of technology's impact on the cultural fabric of societies across the world. Many look with skepticism and concern at the increasing role technology plays in their lives. Postman (1993) has a pessimistic view of technology's impact on cultures and believes that technology is a dangerous enemy that has intruded and destroyed cultures. His argument is not without merit. He suggests that because technology requires change in the environment in order to make it compatible with human needs, it has changed cultures considerably. He terms this "technopoly". According to Evers and Day (1997), there is a chance that culturally appropriate products which preserve cultural values and preferences may not make it to market because people have already been exposed to the less culturally specific versions.

Griffith (1998) believes that when software producers localize software for small indigenous cultures, somehow, elements of that culture are being preserved. Bell (2004) suggests that cultures are more robust and changes occur slowly with regard to technology. In fact, the lack of user acceptance has been the reason for the failure of many information systems. In a comparative study of some 400 university students from the United States and Kuwait, he found that students from the United States had positive attitudes toward computers while Kuwaiti students had less positive attitudes towards computers. Weil and Rosen (1995) carried out an extensive study of technological sophistication and the level of technophobia among 3,392 first year university students at 38 universities in 23 countries. Their main findings indicate that many countries showed a majority of Technophobic students and the differences between the countries were explained by public attitudes towards technology, cultural characteristics, political climate, and the use of computers in the educational system and general availability of technological

innovations. In more recent research on culture, consumption and technology, the use of mobile phones are enabling people to create their own micro-cultures, demonstrating that consumers are repurposing technology for their own use (Plant, 2002; Bell, 2004; Rudich, 2011). Bar, Pisani and Weber (2007) add that mobile phone users go beyond mere adoption to make technology their own and embed it within their social, economic and political practices. All these support Leonardi's (2002) belief that technology is understood in social contexts and that societies determine if technology fits into their cultures. Culture drives technology. As noted by Castells (1999, pg. 9), "social development today is determined by the ability to establish a synergistic interaction between technology innovation and human values".

In summation, contemporary society is characterized by consumption as marked by the shift from a production-driven economy to a consumption-driven economy. As such, corporations have to include the consumer as a significant factor in the production of their goods and services. While culture and consumption have always been interrelated, the advent of global communications technologies adds to the complexity. According to Rothkopf (1997), culture is not static but instead, grows out of a systematically encouraged reverence for selected customs and habits. This view is echoed by Lewis (2007). Central to the interplay of culture, consumption and technology is the issue of personal identity which is in turn influenced by factors in the macro and micro-environments. The following section will situate the mobile phone into this context and lead to the development of the conceptual framework for this study.

2.2 A Brief History of the Mobile Phone

According to Lasen (2003), the first commercial systems were up and running in the 1940s. When it was first introduced, it was highly priced and targeted at business users and also suffered greatly from the lack of capacity. It actually took thirty years for the mobile phone to be accepted into the mainstream community. The first prototypes were fairly crude technologies that suffered from a chronic lack of capacity and thus prevented them from becoming mass-market devices. Car-based radios would broadcast and receive transmissions from a single fixed based station where the radio channel would be connected to a land phone line. The frequencies used by a call could not be reused and were blocked by one call for as far as the radio transmissions were received. There was a separate channel for each call. This technology could not hit mainstream not because of the lack of public interest but the lack of frequency. In 1976, there were 44,000 people in the United States with mobile phones and 20,000 individuals on a waiting list of

between 5 – 10 years. Interestingly, the solution to the capacity problem had already been resolved in 1947 by splitting the coverage area into individual cells and the technological challenges that arose were subsequently met by the late 1960s. However, mobile telephony was delayed throughout the 1970s due to decisions made by governments and telephone companies. As a consequence, the first mass market for a commercial mobile phone system in the United States started only in 1983, 37 years after the first car phone service.

Kopomaa (2000) defines the three stages of the spread of the mobile phone

1. **Class market** (1975- 1990): Mobile phones were expensive and rare; used by sales business people.
2. **Mass market** (1990-1995): Mobile phones became a personal commodity for the general public as low prices made them affordable.
3. **Diversified mass markets** (1995 – present): Mobile phones are manufactured to suit the various lifestyle needs of different groups of consumers.

In many aspects, the uptake of the mobile phone is similar to the adoption pattern of the fixed phone line. But its popularity in contemporary society has exceeded that of a landline. The World Telecommunications Development Report (2002) shows that the mobile phone has contributed to the narrowing of the century-gap in telephone usage between highly developed and less developed nations. Indeed, the relatively low costs and simplicity of the mobile phone have made its spread and reach unique in the history of technology (Plant, 2002). In fact, in remote parts of several developing countries, mobile phone technology has leapfrogged landline technology because of the high costs involved in laying cables and building the basic infrastructure. Townsend (2000) feels that one of the major impacts of the mobile phone stems from its capacity to include partly illiterate mass populations of less developing countries in the southern hemisphere who will never have the means to purchase a computer and were never even connected through traditional fixed phone line networks. By 2008, some 2.5 million Kenyans were able to deposit and withdraw money via their mobile provider's airtime sales agent through text messaging. Harper (2003) believes that the mobile phone is a new type of technology despite its links with Alexander Bell's invention of 1876 as it allows for different types of communication patterns: short calls and messages, the possibility of transmitting a particular experience in real time and the ability to conduct short, productive business conversations. Brown (2001) suggest that the computer is now embedded in the mobile phone as

the latter is an address book, a calendar, an alarm clock, a gaming console and a modem. It is fast becoming a navigation tool determining the coordinates of everyday living (Plant, 2002; Lasen, 2003; Harkin, 2003; Rudich, 2011; Ling, 2012; Saylor, 2012).

2.3 Factor affecting Mobile manufacturing company in the 21st Century

This section highlights pertinent literature that examines factors in the micro and macro environment and how they relate to mobile phone consumption and more specifically, consumer identity. Identity projects continually evolve over time and this identity exploration resides at the threshold of societal life and identity-supporting connections within society. Identity change is often influenced by changes in the external environment and through the use and show of possessions (Stryker, 1980). This constant process of re-evaluating and modifying the self-concept results from a constantly changing environment and changing personal situations. The external environment is represented by contemporary societal life. This is broadly divided into the micro-environment, relating to social networks, personal history and symbolic meaning of products and the macro-environment, relating to globalization. The mobile phone serves as the identity-related possession. Contemporary societal life is influenced by factors in both the micro-environment and macro-environment. This is often in the outward show and use of possessions such as the mobile phone as a reinforcement of one's personal identity.

2.3.1 The micro-environment

The micro-environment represents the immediate environment in the day-to-day life of an individual. The factors in the micro-environment are social networks, personal history and the symbolic meanings of products.

2.3.1.1 Social networks

Research shows that people tend to define their social context locally rather than globally and look to local sources for social recognition and identity. As identity is a product of socialization, friends, family and co-workers provide influential feedback on personal consumption and provide key basis for social comparison (Richins, 1995). An individual belongs to a social network, part of which can be described as a family in terms of its special meaning to the individual (Stacey, 1990). As such, connection to family is significant to an individual's sense of social identity. Even though mobile phones are a ubiquitous part of modern living (Goggin,

2012) and flexibility accorded by mobility (Elliot & Urry, 2010). It allows individuals to extend their networks much wider (Wellman & Lee, 2012), ‘voice calls and text messages remain the bulk of most people’s mobile behavior’ (Ling & Donner, 2009, p. 71). Texting has also developed into a channel where some groups feel comfortable expressing thoughts and feelings that were once reserved for co-present interaction (Ling, 2008). Calls and messages are so ingrained in the normal progression of daily interaction that they become normalized and part of a “connected presence” (Licoppe, 2004), especially in the immediate circle of family and friends (Ling, 2008). According to Castells et al. (2007), texting acts as a catalyst for the construction and reinforcements of peer groups. In fact, Ling (2008) believes that this is the way we develop social cohesion as we engage in perpetual contact in everyday formal interactions. To a large extent, the introduction of the mobile phone has altered the way in which an individual conducts his everyday life as the mechanics of social interaction has changed (Ling, 2008). This ‘dynamic social technology’ (Alexander, 2000) serves as a demonstration of the individual’s social networks. Licoppe and Heurtin (2002) believe that when an individual receives a call on his mobile phone, it reflects that he has not fallen into complete oblivion in his social circle but is still very much connected to his social network. Ling (2012) suggests that the mobile phone provides a taken-for-granted link to the people closest to us such that when we are without it, social and domestic disarray may result. Cox and Leonard (1990) add that phone calls are a powerful reminder of social connectedness with an individual’s social circle, regardless of what is being communicated. Ling (2008) states that the mobile phone strengthens social bonds between family and friends as they engage in perpetual contact, through “connected presence” (Licoppe, 2004). Indeed, the advent of the mobile phone has led to an increase in the number of ‘grooming calls’ or gossip calls, essential to one’s social, psychological and physical well-being (Fox, 2001). The mobile phone serves as a symbolic decoder of ‘fitting in’ with one’s social network and reinforces the individual’s social identity.

Given the mobile phone’s capacity to aid in the retention of primary social relationships over physical distance, the use of mobile phones help to cushion the traumatic experiences of foreign environments as one can still be tightly connected to loved ones at home (Geser, 2004). Individuals who travel or have to live away from home are assured that they can connect with their loved ones even when on the move, regardless of physical proximity. Licoppe and Heurtin (2002) feel that short, frequent and informative calls may strengthen the formation and maintenance of deep bonds not because of their content but the reassurance they create or

reinforce. This relates to the individual's sense of belonging and enhances his sense of self-identity within his social circle of close friends and family.

The need to maintain contact with a large social network is made more convenient with the mobile phone. The mobile phone has equalized the opportunities for communications between moving and non-moving people. Communication no longer occurs from one fixed point to another as with landlines but at different points with a multitude of both moving and still people (Wellman & Lee, 2012). The mobile phone has opened up a new way of establishing and maintaining one's social network. Frequent interactions with one's social network through phone calls and text messages reinforce an individual's social identity. Harper (2003) believes that communication with one's social network will take precedence over other functions the mobile phone provides. Specifically, the use of text messaging provides a less intrusive way of establishing contact with one's social circle when immediate reactions may not be possible (Geser, 2004). Text messaging has become particularly popular with individuals in more conservative cultures as a means to communicate without the need to voice feelings and thoughts (Plant, 2002). Fox (2001) believes that even shy people can utilize text messaging to communicate as they do not have to expose themselves in a highly personalized way. Text messaging also allows one to 'exteriorize' his thoughts spontaneously - communicating his thoughts the moment they arise. This allows the individual to communicate with his social circle at all times and helps to reinforce his social identity. Because text messaging provides the opportunity of delaying the reception and answering at a more appropriate time. Fox (2001) suggests that text messaging allows the individual extra time to formulate his thoughts and express them more clearly. In fact, text messaging is often used for conveying apologies or to communicate things which make one uncomfortable as it offers intimacy of a controlled form, particularly useful for discretion (Ling, 2008). This function allows the user to maintain his social identity while minimizing unpleasant conflicts. Eldridge and Grinter (2001) add that the hundred and sixty character limit for a text message means that short, abrupt messages are acceptable without the preliminary 'How are you?' typical in phone conversations. As such, text messaging can be an efficient way to provide or obtain information from a large group of people in one's social network. It provides a unique way of communicating without the need to say too much (Plant, 2002). It allows for constant communication without being too intrusive. As such, text messages are highly functional for widening the sphere of one's social network by an ever-

changing multitude of peripheral relationships. Text messages also serve as ‘trailers’ for gossip that would be further expanded in a personal face-to-face encounter (Fox, 2001). Texts are widely considered the currency of modern conversations and texting offers just the right amount of access as well as control (Licoppe, 2004; Ling, 2008). In fact, texting remains the most popular use of a mobile phone (Nielsen, 2013). However, there are some drawbacks to the use of mobile phones as a means of reinforcing one’s social identity. The over-reliance on the mobile phone for social connectedness may backfire as a mobile phone that never rings could generate unprecedented loneliness and isolation (Plant, 2002; Ling, 2008; Wellman & Lee, 2012). Just as a phone call is a powerful reminder of social connectedness, the lack of calls could suggest that one has been displaced from one’s social circle. With call screening and voice message systems in place, unreturned calls and messages signal that people do not want to be contacted. This alienation impacts the social identity of the individual who is trying to make the connection. Also, the fluid and spontaneous lifestyle made possible by the mobile phone gets one accustomed to the flexibility of rescheduling (Townsend, 2000), making social life highly volatile and unpredictable as despite all the arrangements, some events never occur (Plant, 2002; Geser, 2004). However, Ling (2004) believes that this flexibility aids in micro coordination to maximize little pockets of time and allows people to make last minute arrangements. Lasen (2003) suggests that the use of mobile phones may alter social distances as calls and messages often function as substitutes for face-to-face interactions. Also, the quality of face-to-face interactions may be compromised by the ‘always-on’ mobile phone.

Interaction with those co-present can be interrupted at any time by a remote other, leading to a scenario of always-on but never there (Plant, 2002). Even a silent mobile phone tends to siphon concentration, aptly labeled the ‘gooseberry effect’ as the receiver may receive a call or message at any time and that would disrupt the existing conversation (Plant, 2002). Turning off the mobile phone in the presence of others shows that one is committed to the present conversation and reinforces the respect the mobile phone user has for the other parties present. However, the thought of others being unable to reach the individual on his mobile phone may serve as a distraction to the individual and impacts his social identity as well (Lasen, 2003). The freedom associated with ‘anywhere, anytime’ becomes a curse when weekends, vacations and sick leave are not completely ‘free’ as one is still reachable (Bachen, 2001) and the person on the end of a line is ‘always there’. As a consequence, the accentuation of the traditional symmetries of social power and control has emerged: employer over employee and parents over children. Thus,

mobile phone users have to contend with increased personal responsibility (Geser, 2004) as excuses of unavailability become less convincing. In addition, the constant and unexpected calls or messages strains the capacity of the individuals to switch roles/identities and may cause unnecessary psychological stress (Geser, 2004; Rudich, 2011).

2.3.1.2 Personal history – maintenance of key life roles and identities

Life projects are the “construction and maintenance of key life roles and identities (such as being a loyal employee, a successful parent)” (Huffman et al. 2000, p.15, 18). These are modified and shaped by factors in global brands and media influences but are more distinctly rooted in personal history and social networks (Lewis, 2007). Over time and through a variety of consumption experiences, consumer learning is reflected in network structures connecting self-related goals and values with specific products and behaviors that satisfy him. The individual in identity construction accumulates experiences with products that assist him in the execution of his multiple roles in life. The mobile phone with its utilitarian functions, is uniquely adaptable and multi-functional (Rudich, 2011; Saylor, 2012), often allowing itself to play useful roles in a wide variety of cultural contexts, social worlds and individual lives. This gives the individual the ability to integrate and structure his life much more efficiently which in turn reinforces his individual identity.

Before the advent of the mobile phone, work and personal life were more distinct, as segregated by work hours and after office hours. With the introduction of the mobile phone, the distinct lines of work and personal life are blurred (Ling, 2001) as individuals become increasingly mobile (Ling & Donner, 2009). Fox (2001) and Ling (2012) believe that the mobile phone serves a lifeline for an individual’s complex everyday life as it aids in the micro-management of his pockets of time. This allows the individual to play both the roles of a mother and an employee. Gergen (2002) believes that the mobile phone can be seen as a technology that empowers one to continue primary social bonds during periods of spatial separation, providing a ‘nomadic intimacy’ by making it possible for those on the move to remain embedded in their personal social networks. This sense of ‘remote belonging’ is important to an individual as it relates to his sense of identity. Many studies indicate that mobile phone usage is subject to further expansion as users gradually change habits and learn to apply the new technology for a growing variety of purposes and in a widening range of situations that constitute modern life (Geser, 2004; Rudich, 2011;). The increasing applications that a mobile phone support makes it possible to incorporate

it to an individual's complex everyday life (Nielson, 2013). The mobile phone provides the individual with the flexibility of rapid role-switching, allowing him to micro-coordinate time, filling time that otherwise might be wasted (Progressive, 2001) as he can play multiple roles simultaneously (Ling, 2012). Lasen (2003) adds that mobile phones facilitate an increased temporal efficiency by flexibility in the use of time. With the context of increasing stress and complexity, the mobile phone serves as a lifeline for the individual, allowing him to perform a myriad of tasks related to both work and private life (Lasen, 2003; Rudich, 2011). This strengthens the individual's sense of identity as he is able to fulfill his multiple roles successfully. At the same time, this 'time softening' allows for last minute gatherings, complicating one's social life by creating many new decision dilemmas associated with 'availability management' (Licoppe & Heurtin, 2002). The fact that one is reachable (Bachen, 2001) as long as his mobile phone is turned on has made it impossible to clearly distinguish between private personal time and social life. Lasen (2003) believes that the mobile phone has in itself become a place where its owner can be found. Even though this seems to suggest the accentuation of traditional symmetries of social power of and control has emerged such as that of employer over employee and parents over children, Ling (2004) highlights how teenagers have found creative ways to circumvent the watchful eyes of parents with their unique uses of both voice communication and text messaging. Lasen (2003) suggests that the possibility of maintaining a continuous connectivity coexists with the constant worry about the continuity of accessibility, concerning unwanted demands, the annoyance of being interrupted and the fear of being controlled. This may add unnecessary stress to an individual's life as he has to try to manage his multiple roles effectively and according to circumstances (Geser, 2004). Rudich (2011) adds that marketers should be wary of intruding onto consumers' personal space or risk annoying loyal customers.

2.3.1.3 Symbolic meaning of products

Individuals cultivate and preserve their identities via the symbolic use of possessions (Belk, 1988). Stryker (1980) believes that identity change is in the use and show of possessions – the external representation of one's identity. The literature on materialism provides a framework which helps to understand the meaning that consumers attach to worldly possessions (Belk, 1985). Conspicuous consumption still plays a significant part in shaping preferences for many products which are purchased or consumed in public context as it reinforces social identity. Recent studies on mobile phone consumption have identified that mobile phones are likely to

provide subjective intangible benefits. They help to convey personal and social identity (both actual and desired) in particular settings and towards various audiences. Kleine and Kleine (1999) add that one's social networks provide the opportunity to learn about and receive feedback about one's identity attempts. As socially shared meanings are important to consumers' choices, the mobile phone has a social function in addition to any other benefits it provides. The mobile phone can also be thought of as a 'prop' to manage particular audiences' impressions (Schlenker, 1980). The value of the mobile phone is motivated by the individual's desire to enhance or support his self-concept through referent identification (Kelman, 1961).

In Plant's (2002) global study, she found that access to a mobile phone and its secrets can function as an emblem of group trust and group solidarity as well as a medium for self-expression for the teenage subcultures. The mobile phone serves as a symbolic decoder of 'fitting in' with one's social network and reinforces the individual's social identity. This supports Kleine and Kleine (1999) belief that identity exploration stems from an outside-in influence. In addition, the physical presence of the device serves as a reminder of the network of friends and loved ones stored within its phonebook (Ling, 2012; Wellman & Lee, 2012). As such, it is kept close to one's body. This sense of attachment lies more in the imagined connections within the phone than the value of the actual connections it facilitates. Palen, Salman and Young (2001) liken the mobile phone to an 'umbilical cord', allowing parents to retain a permanent channel of communication in times of spatial distance.

While anxious parents view this as a means to ensure the safety of their children, children view this as some form of surveillance monitoring, choosing to use the call screening facility to evade parental control (Taylor & Harper, 2003). While there are some who purchase mobile phones simply for functionality purposes, there are some who purchase mobiles phones because of the status that the particular brand or design represents (Katz & Sugiyama, 2006); the phone is not just a tool of convenience, but a way in which consumers express their identity (Katz & Aakhus, 2002). Similar to other fashion objects, the mobile phone is now an item that users customize to suit their sense of self and group affiliation (Katz & Sugiyama, 2006). Indeed, no other device has infiltrated society so widely and is so connected with identity that people see it as a technological extension of themselves (Campbell, 2007). No other medium has been considered so personal (Grant & Kiesler, 2001) that panic arises if it is lost. In a 2003 UK survey, 46 percent of mobile phone users described the loss of their mobile as a form of bereavement (Harkin, 2003). Harper (2003) suggests that to lose one's mobile phone is akin to losing one's connection

to society. The fact that mobile phones are under personal ownership as opposed to fixed-line phones which are considered 'public' utility reinforces the link between mobile phones and individual identity (Grant & Kiesler, 2001). Calls on a fixed line phone can be for any member of the household whereas calls or messages on mobile phones are directed at the individual and for the individual only. In a 5000 person global survey conducted by Qualcomm and Time, 68% of mobile phone users sleep with their phones next to them (Sutter, 2012). This enhances the feelings people have about themselves and makes them feel closely connected to their social networks (Harkin, 2003).

Phone giant Nokia claims that the mobile phone is the most intimate communications device in the modern world. Fortunati (2002) links this intimate relationship between mobile phones and users to the fact that usage of the phone relates to the simultaneous involvement of the ear, mouth and voice. Both physical and emotional attachment to the mobile phone handsets attest to this. Many are afraid to leave home without it and feel uncomfortable when others pursue their mobile phone menus or messages (Licoppe, 2004). Harkin (2003) believes that mobile phones function as comfort objects - antidotes to the hostile terrain of wider society. The fact that one's social network is just a phone call away creates a sense of social connectedness and enhances one's well-being (Plant, 2002; Fortunati, 2005).

The emotional relationship the individual has with the mobile phone can be observed in how many delight in adorning the phones with personalized ringtones and covers (Plant, 2002) and customizing its display (Rudich, 2011). Everything from the color of the handsets to the sound of its ring tone can be given a personal touch. Unlike other modern technologies, the mobile phone lends itself to 'personalization' (Geser, 2004), allowing itself to be an accessory, a fashion statement, an instant messenger, a toy and a social prop all at once. This corresponds with an individual's multiple roles in life and reinforces his individual identity. An interesting study undertaken in the United Kingdom showed that there is a positive correlation between using mobile phones and smoking. While the number of teenagers using mobile phones has increased, the percentage of teens who smoke has also dropped. Pragmatic observers believe that teenagers are chatting more and smoking less because their money is being used to pay their phone bills. Others feel that mobile phones are grown up, glamorous and costly; they offer something to do when one is bored and keeps one embedded in one's social setting (Ling & Donner, 2009). Bautsch et al. (2001) suggests that one reason why so many mobile phone activities occur in the public could be associated with the symbolic display of intense social integration. Having one's

a phone ring in public seems to suggest an individual's importance or popularity (Plant, 2002). Lasen (2003) adds that the mobile phone may also serve as a 'symbolic bodyguard' to suggest to others that the individual may be physically alone but still very much connected to his social network (Plant, 2002). Fox (2001) suggests that the idea of one's social network of family and friends being somehow 'in' the phone means that just touching or holding the phone gives one a sense of being protected and sends a signal to others that one is not vulnerable despite being physically alone. To a certain extent, mobile phones enhance the owner's feeling of increased personal security and safety, and the ability to respond to sudden outside changes (Kopomaa, 2000). Women in several cities in the UK emphasized the value of the mobile phone as a phone-shield against unwanted attention (Plant, 2002). Research among mobile phone users in Norway found that the majority make their initial purchase as a device to increase personal security in the event of an emergency (Harkin, 2003). Harkin (2003) adds that this trust in mobile phones may symbolize a lack of trust in the community at large.

Ironically, users forget that their mobile phones are still dependent on a largely invisible infrastructure that users have no control over. The 'gift-nature' of text messages also contributes to the symbolic meaning of the mobile phone. People tend to save messages they cherish on their mobile phones. The text messages have value which is connected to the giver, the recipient and the context in which the exchange takes place and is retained in material form. This allows one to peruse the messages from loved ones over and over again (Ling, 2004). This relates to an individual's need to feel connected to his social network and reinforces his social identity. Even though the convenience of using the mobile phone has led to 'work to family spillover' (Chesley, 2005), research has shown that texting and calling are primarily used to stay in touch with those within the 'intimate sphere' (Ling, 2008) that includes families, romantic interests and closest friends. Calls and messages on the move allow mobile users to maintain connection to their most important networks. According to Harkin (2003), the mobile phone has given rise to whole new forms of courting ritual. In a 2003 UK survey, 69 per cent of text messages are passed between romantic intimates. Research from Finland shows that text-messages are often shared among intimates as a sign of confidence. On the flip side, the mobile phone also symbolizes infidelity. The device has made it much easier to lie about feelings and intentions and especially whereabouts (Plant, 2002). Tchouaffe (2009) adds that texting may aid in the cheating process as students use their mobile phones to receive information from outside the classroom. As mobile phones become commonplace in the information revolution age (Goggin, 2012; Saylor, 2012),

The physical device itself has less bearing on consumer identity as it becomes an acceptable part of modern everyday life (Ling, 2012). The introduction of digital tablets in recent years also provides another avenue for consumers to partake in social media for connection to their social networks, perhaps diminishing the importance of mobile phones to a certain extent (Saylor, 2012).

2.3.2 The macro-environment

2.3.2.1 Globalization

According to Castells (1997), globalization has always implied a fundamental rethinking of social organization and cultural patterns. As mentioned previously, contemporary society is characterized on two dimensions: outward into geographic space (Hassan, 1999) as evidenced by the rapid movement of capital, labor, goods and services across the world (Friedman, 1999); and inward into culture and society (Hassan, 1999). These can be observed in the global trends in mobile phone consumption. Mobile telephony has moved swiftly from being the technology of a privileged few to an essentially mainstream technology (Castells et al. 2007). The soaring popularity of mobile phones across the globe has made a huge difference to regions where fixed-line telephone services are unavailable, inefficient or prohibitively expensive (Plant, 2002). Townsend (2000) adds that even partly illiterate mass populations in developing nations are enjoying the benefits of being connected through the mobile phone. Indeed, it has become the technology of choice for developing countries in order to reduce their connectivity gap (Castells et al. 2007).

The growth is particularly staggering in developing countries with little “landline” telephone infrastructure. Many remote areas in the third world have gone from having no telecommunications infrastructure to having satellite based communications systems (The Economist, 2008). In remote parts of several developing countries such as Swaziland and Somalia, the mobile phone has been introduced in the form of payphone shops in villages which never had landlines (Plant, 2002). The developing world missed out on much of the excitement of the initial web revolution, the dotcom boom and Web 2.0 because they did not have an internet infrastructure. Thus, the introduction of the mobile phone has created a feeling of equality across the world regardless of age, gender, cultural background or social standing (Puro, 2002). This reinforces one’s social identity. Mobile phone calls can come at any time, any place and in the company of any number of onlookers and eavesdroppers; taking precedence over the

social interactions it interrupts (Plant, 2002; Campbell, 2007). Gergen (2002) notes that when a mobile phone rings, it is the causal relationship with the bystanders that gets broken. Geser (2004) adds that in a public place, mobile phones make it easier for users to find themselves physically near complete strangers as there is a 'virtual exit option' simply by contacting someone on the phone.

Plant (2002) feels that the introduction of the mobile phone has created a 'simultaneity of place' as the public space is becoming a 'common living room' (Kopomaa, 2000) and the home is becoming a communication hub (Bachen, 2001). Tchouaffe (2009) believes that the concept of space is no longer valid. The blurring of the public and private space makes it difficult to control the intrusiveness of mobile phones ringing and conversations (Campbell, 2007) as communication is increasingly dislocated to 'non-places' which have no intrinsic relationship to the messages or messengers involved (Auge, 1995). This requires an adaptation of the social rules of interaction (Lasen, 2003; Campbell, 2007). Mobile phone use facilitates the display of emotions in public settings where those physical expressions used to be absent (Scherer, 2001). Tchouaffe (2009) suggests that the mobile phone promotes a culture of immediacy that empowers the sender. With the need for rapid role-switching, the individual has to grapple with 'impression management' techniques. In Goffman's (1963) study of the apparently insignificant details of social interaction, social interactions are performances with a 'front stage' and a 'backstage'. The immediate surroundings of the individual constitutes his 'front stage' where he needs to present himself in a favorable light and in ways appropriate to a particular role he is playing and to the particular social setting he finds himself in. The ongoing conversation represents the 'backstage' where the individual enjoys his private conversation without the need for 'impression management'. However, it can be difficult to manage the two different situations. On the one hand, the individual needs to interact with the telephonic interlocutor. On the other hand, he needs to interact with the other people in his physical location through some form of body language. One of the obvious consequences is that sometimes the non-verbal gestures do not go along with prevailing circumstances. The mobile phone requires its users to manage the intersection of the real present and the conversational present in a manner that is mindful to both (Plant, 2002; Campbell, 2007). This can be a highly difficult task that can be equally conflicting. Murtagh (2001) and Puro (2002) believe that individuals reinforce their social distance to others by using various nonverbal gestures. Interestingly, Ling (1997) suggests that this has created the new role of a 'hanging bystander' who has to engage in a 'waiting strategy' during a call and

think about how to continue the original interaction once the call has ended. The need to reconcile with respect for privacy for one and others in a public setting and to create a private environment in a public setting can be a complex undertaking. An unanswered phone is frowned upon just as much as long intimate conversations in public settings. Bautsch et al. (2001) consider the involuntary immersion into other people's intimate lives a subtle form of battery. Some businesses and public spaces have devised ways to minimize the impact of such disruptions. New York City passed a law in 2003 fining people whose mobile phones ring during performances. Some cinemas have taken matters into their own hands by setting up jammers to block mobile phone signals (ITU, 2004). Mobile phones have changed the structuring of daily life. This diffusion has occurred worldwide independent of different cultural habits, values and norms. Mobile phones have even penetrated 'techno-phobic' contexts like Italy where computers and other modern technologies are less accepted in society (Fortunati, 2003) and also in Scandinavian countries where people are traditionally introverted and silence is a highly valued quality (Puro, 2002).

In much of the Pacific Asia where human interaction and interconnectivity to loved ones are more highly prized than any notions of privacy, the mobile phone is readily accepted by those with the constant need to feel within reach (Plant, 2002). Cooper (2001) calls the mobile phone an 'indiscrete technology' as it blurs the distinctions between ostensibly discrete domains such as public and private, remote and distant and work and leisure (Ling, 2001). Castells et al. (2007) believes that the system of mobile communication allows for the blurring, mixing and recomposing of a variety of time/space contexts. Individuals have to construct an 'at-home' environment regardless of the physical environment they are in as they are always reachable (Bachen, 2001). The mobile phone has encouraged the use of public spaces for informal social interaction (Campbell, 2007). Places like restaurants, supermarkets and other "polyvalent" place not committed to specific purposes have become enriched with communicative behavior from mobile phone users (Lasen, 2003). Auge (1995) believes that communication is more dislocated to "non-places" which have no intrinsic relationship to the messages or messengers involved and the content of which is determined by the participants rather than at the setting at which the interaction takes place. This constant role-switching affects their social identities considerably and may cause unnecessary psychological stress (Geser, 2004) with the need to grapple with impression management techniques continuously. Lasen (2003) believes that the question of accessibility is directly linked to the mobile phone as a tool of surveillance. Mobile phones serve

as a form of remote background monitoring activity for workers on the move which help with the catch-up period when returning to the office (Green, 2001). Calls made to the office are also a way to avoid being ‘forgotten’ (O’Hara, Perry, Sellen & Brown, 2001). According to Sherry (2001), mobile workers face a combination of two realities: the need to harmonize among multiple flows of activity and the interplay of planned and improvised action. They have to suffer the tension of the “anytime, anywhere” possibilities of communication while on the move. The potential disruptions of the constant availability make the control of access a necessity (Lasen, 2003). Laurier (2001) describes ways of avoiding the undesirable consequences of permanent accessibility by using call screening and voice mail. These services allow one’s time-space to be extended, orienting towards more urgent requests as opposed to the less immediate ones. The widespread use of the mobile phone means that an increasing amount of information is now being stored on handsets. In the case of loss or theft, personal information that is stored on the mobile phone may be subjected to misuse (Saylor, 2012). It is a fact that the criminal class avails more readily and speedily to technological advances than the general population. The mobile phone provides an easy vehicle for trafficking in drugs, arms and women through nearly untraceable networks. Terrorists are particularly technologically proficient. The world of organized crime, facilitated by mobile phone networks, is probably more insidious than statistics indicate (Stiglitz, 2003).

Lasen (2003) believes that the association between sensational crime and new communication devices is not a new phenomenon. The threads that bind the interconnected world where goods and services flow freely also harbor the threats in this increasingly connected world (Stiglitz, 2003). Critics of mobile technologies argue that they are essentially hostile to social life. This context of ‘everyone culture’ (Kroker & Kroker, 1996) can cause ‘civilization skepticism’ as people start to question the progress of technology on the invasion of privacy (Jones, 1997). Since the launch of camera phones and their increasing popularity, people are snapping pictures as and when they fancy and posting them on popular social media sites such as Facebook and Instagram. But when put to criminal intent, these pictures may invade the privacy of those snapped unknowingly. There have been instances of sexual perverts lurking in public toilets, waiting for a chance to take pictures of unsuspecting victims. In Japan, all handsets have to emit a beep of at least sixty-five decibels whenever a picture is taken. This helps to safeguard the privacy of people (ITU, 2004).

2.4. Empirical Review

Some related studies are conducted by different researchers in different parts of the world. But there is no research conducted in the specific issues affecting mobile manufacturing companies with regards to consumer consumption and individual identity in the Ethiopia context yet. However, there are limited numbers of studies conducted in Ethiopia on the adoption of technological innovation. Specifically, Gardachew (2010) conducted research on the opportunities and challenges of E-banking in Ethiopia. The aim of his study was focused on analyzing the status of electronic banking in Ethiopia and investigates the main challenges and opportunities of implementing the E-banking system. The author conducted a survey on the existing operating style of banks and identifies some challenges of using E-banking system, such as, lack of suitable legal and regulatory frameworks for E-commerce and E- payments, political instability in neighboring countries, high rates of illiteracy and absence of financial networks that links different banks.

Wondwossen and Tsegai (2005) also studied the challenges and opportunities of E-payments in Ethiopia; their objective was studying E-payment practices in developing countries, Africa and Ethiopia. The authors employs interview and on site observation to investigate challenges to E-payment in Ethiopia and found that, the main obstacles to the development of E-payments are, lack of customers trust in the initiatives, Unavailability of payment laws and regulations particularly for E-payment, Lack of skilled manpower and Frequent power disruption. According to Wondwossen and Tsegai (2005), an adequate legal structure and security framework could foster the use of E-payments, which is contradicting with the finding of the previous study.

On the other hand the study conducted by Daghfous and Toufaily (2007) on the success and critical factors in adoption of E-banking by Lebanese banks. The research was conducted on the factors that can lead to success the adoption of E-banking and the other factors that can constitute as barrier to its adoption, it focus on the organizational, structural and strategic factors which can accelerate or, on the contrary, slow the adoption of this electronic mode of distribution and communication by the banks, through analyzing the case of the Lebanese market. In order to test the validity of the theoretical framework, structured survey was used, interview questionnaire that was given to E-banking managers or to information technology managers of all the banks on the official list of institutions operating on the Lebanese market, with a total of 57 banks, 31 of

them operate internationally and 26 are strictly local and were used to gather data. The results of their study shows that the organizational variables (bank size, functional divisions, technical staff, technical infrastructure, perceived risks, decision makers' international experience and mastery of innovation) are variables which exert significant impact on the adoption of E-banking, among the structural characteristics, the result revealed that internal technological environment of the bank is a very important factor in determining the adoption of E-banking, also the result shows that banks which are developing in the international scale are more likely to adopt E-banking innovations.

The other descriptive case study analysis conducted by Khalfan *et al* (2006) on 'Factors influencing the adoption of internet banking in Oman, aimed to identify the main potential factors or impediments that are currently inhibiting the incorporation or adoption of E-commerce applications in the Omani Banking sector. Data used in their study were collected using semi structured interviews and survey questionnaires as well as reviewing some bank documents. The results of their study provide a Pragmatic picture about the adoption of E-Commerce applications in the core financial sector domain of Oman. One of the main findings is that security and data confidentiality issues have been a major barrier. The banking sector was reluctant to use E-commerce applications as they felt that transactions conducted electronically were open to hackers and viruses, which are beyond their control.

Finally, the result of the study indicated that the extent of penetration of E-banking in the growth phase of an emerging market has an important correlation with the improvement of commercial performance.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Based on the relatively scarce research on mobile telephony and supported by research on consumer consumption behavior, three factors in the micro-environment and one factor in the macro environment have been identified. These factors and how they relate to mobile phone consumption and more specifically, consumer identity have been explained in above discussed parts of the chapters. The three factors in the micro-environment are social networks, personal history and symbolic meaning of products. The one factor in the macro-environment is globalization. The second stage of the study is the investigative phase through a structured questionnaire.

Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: H_0 – Micro Environment can affect Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

Hypothesis 2: H_1 – Micro Environment can't affect Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

Hypothesis 3: H_2 – Macro Environment can affect Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

Hypothesis 4: H_3 – Macro Environment can't affect Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODS

This chapter clarifies the research methodology used in this study. It covers research design and methodology, tools and sources of data collection, data collection instruments, target population, sample size and sampling techniques and methods of data processing and analyzing.

3.1 Research Approach and Paradigm

The motivation for any form of research can be linked to its philosophical framework. The term ‘research paradigm’ refers to the theoretical blueprint or structure which underpins the research process. It serves as a guide for the researcher as it helps to reflect what is important, reasonable and legitimate in the conduct of the research. According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), a paradigm can be defined as the basic underlying worldview that serves as a map for researchers. The framework provides a sound guiding structure and a range of acceptable tools that aid a researcher in addressing the questions that would be answered by the research. Bryman and Bell (2003) conclude that a research paradigm is a structural blueprint of beliefs that addresses what should be studied, how the research should be conducted and how the results should be appropriately interpreted. As there are numerous paradigms to guide research, the research paradigm, which will be used for this thesis is Deductive. Since the research reveals the cause and relational approach. In addition, it starts from reviewing previously done theories, instead of developing new theories.

3.2 Research Design

Nachmias and Nachmias (1976) describe a research blueprint as a basic scheme of arrangement that serves as a logical guide to aid the investigator in the process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting observations in a cohesive way. The main objective of the research design is to ascertain that the trail that leads to the data collection continually addresses the initial research questions. A good research blueprint will ensure that the researcher can foresee and identify the seemingly infinite decisions regarding the planning and collecting of data, data processing and analysis (Manheim, 1977).

Kvale, S (1996) considers research as a process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting information to provide solutions to questions or problems. For the purpose of this study, research

is defined as a practical investigation or exploration to find out new facts or assemble old facts by scientific ways for the purpose of developing existing theory or its application for real problems. A descriptive and explanatory research design was considered the most suitable approach in view of the nature of the problem being investigated.

The major purpose of descriptive research is to describe characteristics of a certain phenomenon. Descriptive research paints a picture of the specific details of a situation, social setting, or relationship. By giving answers to who, what, when, where, and how questions. For Kohtari (2006) descriptive research aims at describing a situation in terms of its characteristics.

3.3 Target population and Sample size

Population refers to the full set of cases from which a sample is taken (Saunders 2009:21). It refers to the larger group from which individuals are selected to participate in a study. Using the following table, the researcher is considering 0.05% percent margin of error, 95 percent level of precision and a proportion of 1.96 for the maximum possible degree of variability in the sample size will be taken from the target population of 1100. According to Krejcie and Morgan (1970), there is no need of using sample size determination formula for 'known' population since the table has all the provisions one requires to arrive at the required sample size. The total population of Tecno Mobile is 1100 people based on data taken as of Dec 31 /2017 G.C. Sample size refers to the set of all elements belonging to a certain defined group to be studied or to which research results are going to be generalized to. The sample in this study comprises 285 employees of the company.

Table 3.1
Table for Determining Sample Size of a Known Population

N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S
10	10	100	80	280	162	800	260	2800	338
15	14	110	86	290	165	850	265	3000	341
20	19	120	92	300	169	900	269	3500	346
25	24	130	97	320	175	950	274	4000	351
30	28	140	103	340	181	1000	278	4500	354
35	32	150	108	360	186	1100	285	5000	357
40	36	160	113	380	191	1200	291	6000	361
45	40	170	118	400	196	1300	297	7000	364
50	44	180	123	420	201	1400	302	8000	367
55	48	190	127	440	205	1500	306	9000	368
60	52	200	132	460	210	1600	310	10000	370
65	56	210	136	480	214	1700	313	15000	375
70	59	220	140	500	217	1800	317	20000	377
75	63	230	144	550	226	1900	320	30000	379
80	66	240	148	600	234	2000	322	40000	380
85	70	250	152	650	242	2200	327	50000	381
90	73	260	155	700	248	2400	331	75000	382
95	76	270	159	750	254	2600	335	1000000	384

Note: N is Population Size; S is Sample Size *Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970*

This constitutes managerial staff and non-managerial employees including the position of officer, such as Top Managers, Middle level Managers, Division Heads, all departments which include Planning, Contract Administration, Marketing, Procurements and Supply, Legal, Finance and Admin, Human Resource, Project and Technical Teams.

3.4 Sampling Techniques

The researcher has adopted Purposive Non-Probabilistic sampling techniques. This method may allow not excluding the important concerned body and thereby enhance the insight of the researcher to see the problem properly. Purposive or judgmental sampling is used to extract qualitative data and quantitative data. A purposive sampling method enables the researcher to use personal judgment in selecting cases that will best enable him/her to answer research question(s) and meet objectives (Saunders 2009). Denscombe (2007) states that sample, in case of purposive sampling, is hand-picked. It is important when the researcher wishes to select cases that are particularly informative. The study was predominantly using quantitative data supported by structured questionnaires in which data was collected from selected groups. Due to the nature

of data required for the assessment, a quantitative method of inquiry was found meaningful which allows gathering data using different techniques from targeted sources.

3.5 Data Source and Collection tools

In this study both primary and secondary data are collected. Primary data are those which are collected afresh and for the first time, and happen to be original in character (Kohtati 2004:95). Secondary sources are those which are made available such as books, policy documents, reports, articles and company yearbooks.

As sources of primary data, interviews were conducted and questionnaires were distributed. Questionnaires were used to collect data from all employees of the company drawn based on the same purposive sampling. Questionnaires were used in this case since they can be administered to a large number of people at less cost and reach respondents who are not easily approachable. Questionnaires also give respondents adequate time to give well thought out answers (Kohtari 2004).

Dencombe (2007) defines close-ended questionnaires as those which structure the answers by allowing only answers which fit into categories that have been established in advance by the researcher. Since all of the questions demand the level of agreement of the employees, such as a Likert scale going to be used. Five scale formats namely strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. Close ended format is chosen as it is easier and quicker for respondents to answer, easier to compare the answers of different respondents, easier to code and statistically analyze.

The answers for the structured part of the questionnaire are based on Likert-scale of five ordinal measures of agreement towards each statement (from 1 to 5) as shown in the following sections. Likert-scale is important to know respondents' feelings or attitudes for interpretation. The respondents must indicate how closely their feelings match with the question or statement on a rating scale. Accordingly the respondents chose one of the following based on their feelings.

- 5- Strongly Agree
- 4- Agree
- 3- Neutral
- 2- Disagree
- 1- Strongly disagree

Here, the mean ranges are:

For Strongly Agree= from 4.5 up to 5

For Agree= from 3.5 up to 4.4

For Neutral= from 2.5 up to 3.4

For Disagree= from 1.5 up to 2.4

For strongly disagree= below 1.

Documents as sources of secondary data are chosen since they are vital in gaining a comprehensive view of the research problem. The following frames of the data collection procedure and consideration are going to be adopted.

No	Data Sources/participants	Instruments of data collection
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All professional staff of the company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaires
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document review

3.6 Validity and Reliability

3.6.1 Reliability

Reliability refers to a measure of the degree to which research instruments yield consistent results (Mugenda and Mugenda 2003). In this study, reliability was ascertained by pre-testing the questionnaire with a selected sample of employees from the company that was the concern of the study. In different scholars the accepted Cronbach's alpha is .7 and above, thus here the researcher attested that the reliability that it is above the standard and very convenient for the study, by testing questionnaire's reliability test using SPSS Version 23.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.821	39

3.6.2 Validity

The accuracy of data collected largely depended on the data collection instruments in terms of validity. Validity as noted by Robinson (2002) is the degree to which the result obtained from the analysis of the data actually represents the phenomenon under study. Validity was ascertained by having all the objective questions included in the questionnaire.

3.7 Methods of data Analysis

After carefully considering the research questions, the nature of the data needed for the analysis and the prevailing conditions on the research field, quantitative approaches were employed to analyze the collected data.

The quantitative data were being coded, entered to the computer (SPSS software version 23.0), and then computed to produce an aggregated table of results. Descriptive statistics was applied to produce graphs and other numerical and pictorial displays. Interpretation was the next step to integrate views of different respondents on specific issues of discussion. The interpreted quantitative data were integrated at the stage of analysis so that data presentation would be corroborated by the facts generated from both sources.

3.8 Ethical Consideration

According to Saunders et al (2009) ‘The appropriateness of your behavior in relation to the rights of those who become the subject of or are affected by your work’ There should be need high care for Maintaining objectivity, confidentiality and anonymity, because if we do not give concern for this, it is danger at all, in different aspect. Beside, here is attention is given how to process Personal data, Saunders et al (2009) stated that, Research ethics therefore relates to questions about how we formulate and clarify our research topic, design our research and gain access, collect data, process and store our data, analyze data and write up our research findings in a moral and responsible way.

This means that you will have to ensure that the way you design your research is both methodologically sound and morally defensible to all those who are involved. Inevitably, what is morally defensible behavior, as researchers will be affected by broader social norms of

behavior (Zikmund 2000, cited in Saunders et al (2009)). A social norm indicates the type of behavior that a person ought to adopt in a particular situation (Robson 2002; Zikmund 2000, cited in Saunders et al. (2009)). However, as Cooper and Schindler (2008) recognise, the norms of behavior that guide moral choices can in reality allow for a range of ethical positions. The issue of plagiarism is highly focused and forbidden to be done in such a way.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter contains the analysis of the data gathered from the respondents through questionnaires and the description of the respondents. The responses of the respondents were tabulated, changed into percentage and interpretation was given based on the percentage. This chapter describes the analysis and interpretation of the collected data. Out of the 285 questionnaires distributed to Tecno Mobile Company employees in their Addis Ababa branches. Data collected from the survey questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive analysis, correlation & regression with the help of Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS v. 23.0).

4.1 Demography of the Participants

Table 4.1 Respondent Demographic Data

Demography	Indicator	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	175	61.4	61.4	61.4
	Female	110	38.6	38.6	100.0
	Total	285	100.0	100.0	
Age group	21-30 years	240	84.2	84.2	84.2
	31-40 years	15	5.3	5.3	89.5
	41-50 years	20	7	7	96.5
	Above 50 years	10	3.5	3.5	100.0
	Total	285	100.0	100.0	
Education Level	Master's Degree	11	3.9	3.9	3.9
	College Diploma	5	1.8	1.8	5.6
	BA Degree	269	94.4	94.4	100.0
	Total	285	100.0	100.0	
Experience in the company	1- 2 years	241	84.6	84.6	84.6
	3 – 4 years	43	15.1	15.1	99.6
	Over 5 years	1	.4	.4	100.0
	Total	285	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that from the total 285 respondents or participants, 110 (38.6%) of them were females and 175 (61.4%) of them were males. The respondents indicated that 15(5.3%) of the respondents were in the age group of 31-40, the majority respondents almost 240 (84.2%) of them were coming in the age category of 21-30, still 20 (7 %) of the respondents were in the age group of 41-50 and the rest 10 (3.5 %) of the total respondents were found in the category of above 50 years. They narrated that the level of education of respondents 11 (3.9%) of the respondents have a master's degree, 269 (94.4%) replied as they have a degree and the rest 5 (1.8 %) of them have college diploma in the organization employment opportunities. All participants of the study had experience of work in the company for more than one year. Especially as the above table shows, the majority of the respondents, 84.6% and above, have an experience of up to five years. Thus all the above shows that they have great value in adding the validity of the data because they are young and educated as well have a minimum two years of experience that has detailed understanding about the performances of the company.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Analysis for Social Network

Table 4.2 Social Network Data Analysis

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The mobile phone is the primary means in which I stay in contact with my social network of friends and family	285	4.58	.609
The mobile phone helps me to keep in contact with friends and family when I am out of the country or not within physical proximity of the	285	4.56	.652
The mobile phone allows me to partake in last minute social gatherings	285	4.47	.715
I have used my mobile phone to convey apologies or communicate bad news	285	3.98	1.009
Text messaging is a great way to receive or give out information to my social network	285	4.42	.690
The mobile phone provides a convenient means to reschedule planned activities	285	4.36	.722
The mobile phone sometimes functions as a substitute for face-to-face interactions	285	4.22	.804
I have been left hanging in mid-sentence in a conversation because the other party received a phone call/text message.	285	4.16	.914
I have interrupted a conversation to answer my mobile phone	285	4.17	.813
I have answered personal calls/text messages while I am at work	285	4.21	.834
Valid N (listwise)	285		

Table 4.2 draws a picture on the mean figures accrued by each of the items under social network. It can be deduced from the above that most of the items registered have an agreement. Therefore, we can conclude that the social network has a great impact on the company performance as one of the mobile manufacturing industry factors. At the organizational level, social networks are critical to a large extent, because the introduction of the mobile phone has altered the way in which an individual conducts his everyday life as the mechanics of social interaction has changed (Ling, 2008). This ‘dynamic social technology’ serves as a demonstration of the individual’s social networks (Alexander, 2000). Furthermore, Licoppe and Heurtin (2002) believe that when an individual receives a call on his mobile phone, it reflects that he has not fallen into complete oblivion in his social circle but is still very much connected to his social network. The reason being is that social networks are important to influence individuals’ choice to work with an organization.

4.2.2 Descriptive Analysis for Personal History

Table 4.3 Personal History Data Analysis

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I use my mobile phone every day.	285	4.45	.752
The mobile phone helps me to coordinate between the different roles I play in life (Employer/employee/parent/child/colleague etc.)	285	4.45	.742
The mobile phone helps me to micro-manage little pockets of time.	285	4.21	.821
The mobile phone allows me to perform a variety of roles (both work and personal) when I am on the move	285	4.34	.761
I have used the functions of the mobile phone to enhance the management of my life (e.g. clock, calendar, mobile mail etc.)	285	4.09	.848
I have used my mobile phone to lie about my whereabouts.	285	4.13	.968
The mobile phone is the best way to reach me.	285	4.15	.784
I will always own a mobile phone.	285	4.20	.870
Valid N (listwise)	285		

The statistics from table 4.3 the researcher can conclude from the mean figures that all of the items put up under personal history attracted an agreement. Therefore, we can say the personal history as a factor of mobile manufacturing companies has a great influence on the involved sector that they should work on, so as to boost the organizational performance. Thus, every company who looks for in the sector should give very crucial attention toward the intended factor, as it has a very significant role in the firm performance. This also was stated by ling (2001) and Ling & Donner (2009), before the advent of the mobile phone, work and personal life were more distinct, as segregated by work hours and after office hours. With the introduction of the mobile phone, the distinct lines of work and personal life are blurred, as individuals become increasingly mobile. Additionally, Fox (2001) and Ling (2012) believe that the mobile phone serves a lifeline for an individual's complex everyday life as it aids in the micro-management of his pockets of time. Therefore the company of mobile manufacturing should have a great look on the matter so as to cope up with the given competition to sustain in the business.

4.2.3 Descriptive Analysis for Symbolic Meaning of Products

Table 4.4 Symbolic Meaning of Products Data Analysis

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The mobile phone is a common technological device among my social network of friends and family.	285	4.09	.873
I feel an emotional loss when my mobile phone is lost/misplaced/stolen.	285	4.26	.814
It is important that my mobile phone is personalized to suit my needs.	285	4.27	.868
The physical presence of the mobile phone serves as a reminder of the network of friends and loved ones stored within my phonebook.	285	4.24	.869
I have used the mobile phone to screen calls and evade unpleasant situations	285	4.20	.867
I feel uncomfortable when others pursue my mobile phone menus and messages without my knowledge or permission	285	4.35	.744
I feel more secure when I have my mobile phone with me because it assures that help is just a phone call away	285	4.21	.843
A constantly ringing mobile phone suggests that the person has an intense social network.	285	4.20	.859
I have used the mobile phone as a shield against unwanted attention.	285	4.21	.872
I save important messages on my mobile phone	285	4.11	.885
The mobile phone is a positive and important part of my everyday life.	285	4.14	.946
Valid N (listwise)	285		

Table 4.4 shows a picture on the mean figures accrued by each of the items under symbolic means of product. It can be said from the above that most of the items registered have an agreement. Therefore, we can conclude that symbolic means of product have a great impact on the company performance as one of the mobile manufacturing industry factors. As Plant's (2002) global study found, access to a mobile phone and its secrets can function as an emblem of group trust and group solidarity as well as a medium for self-expression. Hence The mobile phone serves as a symbolic decoder of 'fitting in' with one's social network and reinforces the individual's social identity. Therefore the company of mobile manufacturing should have a great look on the matter so as to cope up with the competition to be sustained in the business.

4.2.4 Descriptive Analysis for Globalization

Table 4.5 Globalization Data Analysis

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Hearing someone talk on the mobile phone in a public place does not bother me	285	4.15	.879
Hearing someone talk on the mobile phone in prohibited places does not bother me.	285	4.20	.965
I have received unsolicited promotions/advertisements/calls on my mobile phone.	285	4.09	1.029
I have used my mobile phone to participate in promotional activities.	285	3.96	1.084
The mobile phone is useful for informing me about activities that cater to my interests.	285	4.12	.901
I feel comfortable using the mobile phone because it has gained social acceptance.	285	4.18	.942
Watching/observing how others utilize the mobile phone has taught me new ways of using mine	285	4.26	.898
I have given out my mobile phone number so that my favorite stores/mails/activity clubs can reach me to inform me of new product arrivals/activities	285	4.17	.865
Human interaction and interconnectivity to loved ones are more important than privacy	285	4.28	.826
Text messaging is an efficient way of contacting those on my social network when I have information to share.	285	4.09	.889
Valid N (listwise)	285		

From the data of table 4.5 the researcher can conclude from the mean figures that all of the items put up under globalization attracted an agreement. Therefore, we can say that globalization as a factor of mobile manufacturing companies has a great influence on the involved sector that they should consider, so as to boost the organizational performance. Thus, every company who looks for in the sector should give very crucial attention toward the intended factor, as it has a very significant role in the firm performance. This also was stated by (Campbell, 2007) that the

Mobile phones have encouraged the use of public spaces for informal social interaction and Places like restaurants, supermarkets and other “polyvalent” places not committed to specific purposes have become enriched with communicative behavior from mobile phone users (Lasen, 2003). Additionally, Geser (2004) said that in a public place, mobile phones make it easier for users to find themselves physically near complete strangers, as there is a ‘virtual exit option’ simply by contacting someone on the phone. Therefore the company of mobile manufacturing should have a great look on the matter so as to cope up with the competition to be sustained in the business.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

Table 4.6 Correlation Data Analysis for all variables

		Social network	Personal History	Symbolic Meaning of Products	Globalization
Social network	Pearson Correlation	1	.815	.880**	.831*
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.464	.001	.013
	N	285	285	285	285
Personal History	Pearson Correlation	.815	1	.874**	.851
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.464		.002	.193
	N	285	285	285	285
Symbolic Meaning of Products	Pearson Correlation	.880**	.874**	1	.867**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.001	.002		.002
	N	285	285	285	285
Globalization	Pearson Correlation	.831*	.851	.867**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.013	.193	.002	
	N	285	285	285	285

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

The above table indicates that respondents replied that on the factor of mobile manufacture company show that have the highest correlation with each other on the company performance, if every company look to invest on mobile industry this is the stepping stone with other factors which are not done in this study. The result also depicted the influence of each variable with a score of 80% as each of them are importantly inter-dependent so as to determine the success of a company. Additionally, the result has portray each variable have perfect correlation with their

own as it had seen 1(100%) on the diagonal. Thus, the selected factors have a crucial role on the mobile manufacturing company to get the best competitiveness from their investment which in turn increases organizational performance. This is because the external environment is represented by contemporary societal life. It is broadly divided into the micro-environment, relating to social networks, personal history and symbolic meaning of products and the macro-environment, relating to globalization. Thus, a mobile phone serves as the identity-related possession. Furthermore, Contemporary societal life is influenced by factors in both the micro-environment and macro-environment.

4.4 Assumption Test

Siegel and Castellan (1988) assert that the null hypothesis is usually formulated to express the purpose of being rejected; it is the opposite of an alternative hypothesis that one is attempting to prove. The null hypothesis is rejected, in favor of the alternative hypothesis, if its associated probability of occurrence is equal to or less than some small probability (p). The level of significance of 0.05 is selected for this research.

Estimated Distribution Parameters

		Social network	Personal History	Symbolic Meaning of Products	Globalization
Normal Distribution	mean	4.31	4.25	4.21	4.15
	Std. deviation	.273	.325	.339	.374

The cases are unweighted.

Accordingly we can conclude that there is a healthy or positive distribution of the factor which has been collected from the respondent that can be concluded it is under normal distribution of scaling. Hence any improvements in practices toward the accomplishment of the intended factor are positively contributed in enhancing organizational performance of mobile companies. Thus, the researcher is in the right position so as to undertake regression analysis. For this reason the regression analysis for the study was done and observed that the result was in agreement with other analysis.

4.5 Regression Analysis

4.5.1 Regression Analysis for Micro-Environment Factor

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.590 ^a	.348	.346	.18428

a. Predictors: (Constant), Micro Environment factor

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.140	1	5.140	98.362	.000 ^b
	Residual	9.610	283	.034		
	Total	14.750	284			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Micro Environment factor

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.364	.231		5.900	.000
	Micro Environment factor	.667	.054	.590	12.303	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

From the regression analysis we can see that there is a positive statistical relationship between micro-environment factor (the independent variable) and Customer mobile consumption and individual identity (the dependent variable). As the table above presents, the model summer of determination (R-squared) indicates the proportionate amount of variation in the response variable (mobile manufacturing company performance) explained by the independent variable (micro-environment factor) in the linear regression model. Similarly, From the ANOVA table it has been determined that $F = 98.36$ and Sig. is .000 which confirms that micro-environment factors have significant effect on mobile manufacturing company performance. Hence the result

depicted that the hypothesis micro-environment regarding Customer mobile consumption and individual identity of the mobile manufacturing company have significant effect on organizational performance. On the coefficient table we find the beta value which measures how strongly each independent variable influences the dependent variable. Thus a unit increase in micro-environment factor leads to .59 increases in Customer mobile consumption and individual identity of the mobile manufacturing company other things being 41% constant. Therefore, **Hypothesis-1**; H₀: Micro Environment can affect Customer mobile consumption and individual identity is acceptable.

4.5.2 Regression Analysis for Macro-Environment Factor

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.900 ^a	.811	.810	.09935

a. Predictors: (Constant), Macro Environment Factor

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.957	1	11.957	95.418	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.793	283	.010		
	Total	14.750	284			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Macro Environment Factor

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.928	.066		29.338	.000
	Macro Environment Factor	.549	.016	.900	34.805	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer mobile consumption and individual identity

From the above regression analysis we can see that there is a positive statistical relationship between macro-environment factor (the independent variable) and Customer mobile consumption and individual identity (the dependent variable). As the table above presents, the model summer of determination (R-squared) indicates the proportionate amount of variation in the response variable (mobile manufacturing company performance) explained by the independent variable (macro-environment factor) in the linear regression model. Similarly, From the ANOVA table it has been determined that $F = 95.41$ and Sig. is $.000$ which confirms that macro-environment factors have significant effect on mobile manufacturing company performance. Hence the result depicted that the hypothesis macro-environment regarding Customer mobile consumption and individual identity of the mobile manufacturing company have significant effect on organizational performance. On the coefficient table we find the beta value which measures how strongly each independent variable influences the dependent variable. Thus a unit increase in macro-environment factor leads to $.90$ increases in Customer mobile consumption and individual identity of the mobile manufacturing company other things being 10% constant. Therefore,

Hypothesis 3: H_3 – Macro Environment can affect Customer mobile consumption and individual identity is acceptable.

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

Introduction

This chapter provides the summary of the findings of the study, conclusions drawn from findings and recommendations based on the findings. A conclusion drawn was deduced from analysis and objectives set for the research. The area for further research was also suggested in this chapter.

5.1 Summary of the Study

From the total 285 respondents of the questionnaire, where 38.6% were females and 61.4% were males, we can summarize the effects of the micro-environmental and macro-environmental factors on mobile manufacturing companies from the data analysis and interpretation.

Social network is one of the micro environmental factors, which had a great impact on the company performance as one of the mobile manufacturing industry factors. The need for connectivity and social interaction has contributed much for social networks to be one of the factors affecting mobile manufacturing companies.

Personal history is another micro environmental factor, which played a major role in affecting mobile manufacturing companies. The fact that the mobile phone can be used in various occupations like to manage family, work, friendly interactions make it a must have device for the public and hence it will affect the mobile manufacturing companies in a great manner. So mobile manufacturing companies should work on it, so as to boost the organizational performance.

Symbolic means of product also had a great impact on the company performance as one of the micro environmental factors affecting mobile manufacturing industries. The attachment people have to their mobile phones is increasing greatly, with the ability to store personal and dear information in ones mobile phone make the device more attached and emotionally connected to the user, Hence we can consider symbolic means of product on the mobile phone as a factor to mobile manufacturer companies.

Globalization is a major macro environmental factor on mobile manufacturing companies and has a great influence on the involved sector. With mobile phones being common in every place, it has given the impression that everyone is okay with the use of mobile phones and that it has become a common trend, hence it has become one of the factors that affect mobile manufacturing industries.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion this research has found that micro and macro environmental factors play a great role in affecting mobile manufacturing industries. From the micro environmental factors social networks indicate that the mobile phone is one of the primary means in which people stay in contact with their social network of friends and family and use it in their day to day networking activity with people. Personal history indicates the use of the mobile phone in sync with different personalities, roles in the day to day life of the user. symbolic means of product has also been identified as the major factors included in the micro environmental factor, symbolic means of product which depicts the intimacy of a user to his/her mobile phone and also measures the degree of value the phone has to the user. On the other hand globalization has been identified to play a great role in affecting mobile manufacturing industries as it is categorized in macro environmental factors affecting mobile manufacturers. Globalization indicates that it is common for many people to own mobile phones and also the use of it in a public place has become a common phenomena.

5.3 Recommendations

As this research concludes I have some recommendations, which I observed, study gap areas and specific areas that mobile manufacturers should focus on.

Since the four micro and macro environmental factors that are identified in this research have been proved to impact mobile manufacturers, they should take them into consideration while designing the mobile phone. For example, since social networks are one of the factors, the mobile manufacturers should include in the phone social apps like Viber, Facebook, Whatsapp etc. And also for the Ethiopian market there should be utilities built for the locals in the language they understand, apps and games like Amharic dictionary, Ethiopian calendar, Amharic keyboard which will make the mobile phone more than a calling apparatus and more like an interacting friend.

Symbolic means of product being as one of the factors indicate the attachment people have with their mobile phones, hence using the mobile phone for advertising and marketing strategy is a sure way to get noticed and promote products. SMS marketing, in-app advertisements and mobile targeted promotions will have a great impact for promoters so they should use it as one of their marketing strategies.

Finally I recommend that more studies be done in this area, as there could be other unstudied factors that could affect mobile manufacturers in general.

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Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Program- MBA

Questionnaires filled by all selected Employee of the Company Dear Respondent,

My name is Epherem Asnake; I am conducting a research on Factor affecting Mobile manufacturing companies with regards of consumer consumption and individual identity at Tecno Mobile Company in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. You have been selected to take part in this research because you have a role in your company and any information given will be treated with utmost confidence and shall only be used for academic purposes. Thus you are kindly requested to give your valuable time to give your value adding response for this questionnaire. Your cooperation will be highly appreciated.

Thank you for your kind cooperation in filling the questionnaire.

► Tick and fill where appropriate

❖ Section A: Background Information

1) Indicate your position

2) Indicate you gender: Male [] Female []

3) Please indicate your age

21-30 years [] 31-40 years []

41-50 years [] above 50 years []

5) Indicate your highest level of education

Master's Degree [] College Diploma []

BA Degree [] others (specify).....

6) How long have you been in employment with this firm?

1- 2 years [] 3 – 4 years [] Over 5 years []

Indicate the extent of your agreement with respect to each of the following statements by marking 'X' in the box of your choice.

5=strongly agree, 4=agree, 3=moderately agree, 2=Disagree, and 1=strongly disagree

Social Networks

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1
1. The mobile phone is the primary means in which I stay in contact with my social network of friends and family.					
2. The mobile phone helps me to keep in contact with friends and family when I am out of the country or not within physical proximity of them.					
3. The mobile phone allows me to partake in last minute social gatherings.					
4. I have used my mobile phone to convey apologies or communicate bad news.					
5. Text messaging is a great way to receive or give out information to my social network.					
6. The mobile phone provides a convenient means to reschedule planned activities.					
7. The mobile phone sometimes functions as a substitute for face-to-face interactions.					
8. I have been left hanging in mid-sentence in a conversation because the other party received a phone call/text message.					
9. I have interrupted a conversation to answer my mobile phone.					
10. I have answered personal calls/text messages while I am at work.					

Personal History

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1
1. I use my mobile phone every day.					
2. The mobile phone helps me to coordinate between the different roles I play in life (Employer/employee/parent/child/colleague etc.).					
3. The mobile phone helps me to micro-manage little pockets of time.					
4. The mobile phone allows me to perform a variety of roles (both work and personal) when I am on the move.					
5. I have used the functions of the mobile phone to enhance the management of my life (e.g. clock, calendar, mobile mail etc.).					
6. I have used my mobile phone to lie about my whereabouts.					
7. The mobile phone is the best way to reach me.					
8. I will always own a mobile phone.					

Symbolic Meaning of Products

Indicator	5	4	3	2	1
1. The mobile phone is a common technological device among my social network of friends and family.					
2. I feel an emotional loss when my mobile phone is lost/misplaced/stolen.					
3. It is important that my mobile phone is personalized to suit my needs.					

4. The physical presence of the mobile phone serves as a reminder of the network of friends and loved ones stored within my phonebook.					
5. I have used the mobile phone to screen calls and evade unpleasant situations.					
6. I feel uncomfortable when others peruse my mobile phone menus and messages without my knowledge or permission.					
7. I feel more secure when I have my mobile phone with me because it assures that help is just a phone call away.					
8. A constantly ringing mobile phone suggests that the person has an intense social network.					
9. I have used the mobile phone as a shield against unwanted attention.					
10. I save important messages on my mobile phone.					
11. The mobile phone is a positive and important part of my everyday life.					

Globalization

Indicator	5	4	3	2	1
1. Hearing someone talk on the mobile phone in a public place does not bother me.					
2. Hearing someone talk on the mobile phone in prohibited places does not bother me.					
3. I have received unsolicited promotions/advertisements/calls on my mobile phone.					
4. I have used my mobile phone to participate in promotional activities.					

5. The mobile phone is useful for informing me about activities that cater to my interests.					
6. I feel comfortable using the mobile phone because it has gained social acceptance.					
7. Watching/observing how others utilize the mobile phone has taught me new ways of using mine.					
8. I have given out my mobile phone number so that my favorite stores/emails/activity clubs can reach me to inform me of new product arrivals/activities.					
9. Human interaction and interconnectivity to loved ones are more important than privacy.					
10. Text messaging is an efficient way of contacting those on my social network when I have information to share.					